

Multiple perspectives of sustainability	Balance between environmental-economic-social dimensions	
	Circular economy	
	Environmental concerns	minimal
		no footprint
		reuse
	Political strategy	
	Social dimension	Employee wellbeing
	Survive longer	
	Environmental- Social- Technical dimensions	cloud
		code reusability
energy consumption		
reuse computer parts		
Code efficiency		
	good SE practices	
Data Availability		
Motivators to incorporate Sustainability	Improved dependency team communications	
	Extra workload	lack of documentation
		duplicated work
		deadlines
		pressure due to last minute changes
		lack of staff
		No access to online resources
	Organisational benefits	Improved contingencies (requirements and deadlines)
		competition with other companies
	Data Availability	
Streamlined processes	reactive teams over proactive	
	inefficient use of hardware (multiple production environments)	
	Improper agile implementation	
Potential Trade-offs	Departmental profits vs developer workload	

	Organisational profits vs employee satisfaction	contributor to massive fossil fuel companies just a PR
	Risk control (E.g., Security vs Sustainability)	
	Deadline vs Sustainability	
	Efficient code vs Readability	
	Functionality vs Sustainability	
	Technical debt vs Sustainability	
	Challenges in integrating SuSE practices	Clients don't care
Mindset		accept more workload to please managers fear of improper implementation
Could add additional costs		
May increase bottlenecks		
Legacy systems		
Not considered as a priority		
Disturbance to work life balance		
Poor leadership		
Unawareness of sustainability		
Time pressure		
Dedicated Sustainability Team	Delegated ownership as a benefit	
	Knowledgeable leadership	
	Less workload for the middle managers	
	Difficulties to put into practice	
	May not drive large workforce	
	Poor leadership can add new challenges	
Migration to the Cloud as a sustainability solution	Good data redundancy techniques	
	Optimised infrastructure	less infrastructure on premise no need for maintenance of hardware
		easy to scale and flexible

	Low operational costs and low employee training costs as organisational benefit	
	Pushes developers to be sustainable	
	Helps in developer personal growth	